

Data Management Plan for the Project "Practical applications and limitations of quantum search"

Version 1

Description

This data management plan covers the data collected, generated and maintained during the course of the project "Practical applications and limitations of quantum search" of the 1.1.1.9 Research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/206 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research". In this project we plan to find novel methods of quantum search techniques by developing new algorithms and data structures for practical problems with various real-world applications. The main goal is to utilize various fundamental quantum search frameworks to provide new implementable quantum algorithms with provable quantum advantage over the classical (deterministic and probabilistic) algorithms, with outlook to the near-future quantum devices. The secondary goal is to give provable limitations for cases where the quantum improvement is impossible or limited.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

1.1.1.9 Research application
No.1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/206 of the
Activity "Post-doctoral
Research"

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, Roma Tre University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan for the Project "Practical applications and limitations of quantum search"

Description:

This data management plan covers the data collected, generated and maintained during the course of the project "Practical applications and limitations of quantum search" of the 1.1.1.9 Research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/206 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research". In this project we plan to find novel methods of quantum search techniques by developing new algorithms and data structures for practical problems with various real-world applications. The main goal is to utilize various fundamental quantum search frameworks to provide new implementable quantum algorithms with provable quantum advantage over the classical (deterministic and probabilistic) algorithms, with outlook to the near-future quantum devices. The secondary goal is to give provable limitations for cases where the quantum improvement is impossible or limited.

Researchers:

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Roma Tre University

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: 1.1.1.9 Research application No.1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/206 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research"

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: [Public](#)

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Time-space computational complexity of the hypercube path quantum dynamic programming algorithm

The data set for the work on the Quantum Time-Space tradeoffs for Exponential Dynamic Programming.

We will implement a program that computes the time complexity of our quantum algorithms with fixed constrained amount of QRAM space. For each allowed amount of space S , our program will compute the running time T of our quantum dynamic programming algorithm.

The data set will contain the program source code and the generated data in a txt format, containing the obtained (S,T) complexities.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

One of the main goals of the project is to reduce the (expensive) amount of Quantum RAM memory used by the quantum dynamic programming algorithm proposals, while keeping the quantum algorithms faster than classical.

One of the intended methods to obtain such efficient tradeoffs (quantum hypercube path dynamic programming) does not allow for explicit complexity estimates. The running time for this method depends on optimizing many parameters. Therefore, to prove the performance benefit of our method, we will write a computer program that finds the optimal parameters and computes the respective running time of the algorithms.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Programme source code
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The question studied in the project is novel for which there has been no previously generated data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in theoretical quantum computing, industry professionals interested in implementing existing quantum algorithms.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

The data is generated using a computer program and the output is to be openly available to the public, easily available online on Zenodo, including the DOI identifier.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any browser to access the Zenodo repository. The data set will be given in txt format.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

Data record in the Zenodo repository: zenodo.org/records/17151432.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data will be given in a txt format in an easily parseable way.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

The data set will be constituted by be a simple list of numeric pairs.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Chosen to maximize the availability and reusability of the data.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-05-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2031-12-31

No ending date, but at least 2 years after the end of the project.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

There are no additional expenses expected for the availability and maintenance of the data, since it will be publicly available on Zenodo.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jevgēnijs Vihrovs (0000-0002-3143-2610)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The costs are not expected, since the data obtained in this project is expected to be computer generated and then openly published in free-to-use online repositories.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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